

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES.

Zubaydullayeva Zarina Erkinovna

an English teacher at Tashkent Academic
Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article provide information about investigating the advantages of teaching English through games. Language games can help students in building a good relationship with the new language. Teachers should change their role from instructors who dominate the class into educators whose role is to help, guide and support the students to acquire the foreign language.

Key words: Investigate; advantages ;games; foreign language; output.

English is the language of international communication that has been used in various countries in the world as a global communication tool. In the current era of globalization, English is felt to have a significant role, so that English becomes one of the languages that must be mastered, not least in Indonesia. The influence of globalization has made Indonesian citizens more active in learning English. The active learning is inseparable from the role of schools that implement learning programs that emphasize the ability of students to master a foreign language; one of them is English. This also happens in other countries including Indonesia as a consequence of the progress of English, where governments throughout the world actively support learning English for their citizens. However, because of the broad and complex scope of English, not a few people find it difficult to understand English. This is also experienced by most students in schools. They tend to dislike learning English because it is difficult to understand. Because of that, many schools are starting to implement learning methods that can support the convenience of students in understanding or understanding English, so that in the end the English language can be one of the lessons preferred by students in schools. One method that can be an alternative to making learning English easier and more enjoyable is by

learning while playing, which is through certain games. Learning through games can provide several benefits.

First, what is learned by students is not only in the form of mere knowledge of reason but experienced in real terms; such experiences are difficult to forget. Second, the lessons provided are pleasantly accepted, because they are related to the nature of the game which is entertaining and joyful. Thus, the possibility of student rejection of what is taught can be minimized.

Third, because the game is fun, playing at the same time generates excellent interest for students about certain things or topics. Well-designed games (games) will develop students' skills in certain cases. Actually, in learning languages, the principle is the application or use. And through games (games) this principle will be more effectively applied. Games are not merely synonymous with the activities of small children. The learning process while playing is also suitable for all ages because methods like this can increase the interest and motivation to learn English as well as arouse the learning atmosphere to be more interactive for all people of all ages. With games, learning English becomes more exciting, fun, and not boring. This is certainly different if you use the lecture method or discussion. Through fun activities such as games, it is hoped that it can arouse students' interest in learning English and be able to understand English quickly and easily.

Here are some samples of games:

Whisper Race. As the name implies, this game relies on memory. First, divide the students into two teams. One of the team members was given a list of words they needed to memorize. Then the list of words is whispered to the member of one other team. The last member must mention the complete list of words. The team that removes one word from the list of words that have been given is declared defeated.

Hide and Seek. This game can train the use of prepositions in English. Here is the way this game works. First, a participant was asked to leave the class while the other participants were tasked with hiding items. Then, participants who came out were asked to find the location of objects that were hidden by giving questions. What's

Missing? This game uses picture media in the form of a puzzle. Each participant competes to be able to guess the missing pieces of the image by submitting the appropriate answers to English grammar.

Action Game. This game relies on gestures. Select one of the participants to read a story and then try to practice each part of the word in the story that can be practiced. This type of game can also train a wealth of English vocabulary owned. For those who mistakenly practice, give a little humorous punishment.

Game Market. This type of game tests participants to be able to make good sentence compositions. Give the first sentence whose ideas lead to shopping activities on the market, for example. Note that each participant gives a sentence, whether the composition of the grammar, mastery of vocabulary and pronunciation are good. By correcting each other, we can also learn.

The responses from the students were positive where the students felt the benefits gained after learning English by using games. Generally, using games in learning English have many benefits; they are:

1. Increasing students' understanding of the importance of learning English.
2. Extending the students' insights, especially the teachers regarding the method of learning English while playing.
3. Motivating students and teachers to apply games as a method in the class.

Based on the notes provided by the students (attached), there are several suggestions related to the implementation of games in learning English, they are:

1. application in learning English.
2. Focus on introducing the appropriate games in learning English that can make students easy and quick to understand English.

Games can be a very worthwhile teaching element. A successful game is successful because of the reason that it is based on specific time allocation, it has clear relevance to the material, there is appropriateness to all members of the class, and ultimately, the enjoyment of the learners is increased through their active engagement with the language. The idea of using games in teaching does not seem

to be widely accepted and implemented although its profitability has been proposed and justified as early in the seventieth century. There has been a misconception that all learning should be serious in nature. In fact, using games is an important tool that allows language teachers to add colours to their classrooms by providing challenge and entertainment. They are particularly valuable for beginners as a source of cognition that helps them adopt sounds and rhythms and comprehend the foreign language.

Used literature:

1. Qodirberganovna, A. N. РОЛЬ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ И СТУДЕНТОВ В КОММУНИКАТИВНОМ МЕТОДЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЯЗЫКА В КЛАССЕ THE ROLE OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSROOM. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на, 45.*
2. Adamboeva, N. (2023). ASPECTS OF AXIOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS. *Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA»*, (March 10, 2023; Valencia, Spain), 163-166.
3. Qodirberganovna, A. N. (2023). Representation of Maximums in Axiolinguistic Evaluation of Politeness Category in Uzbek and English Languages. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(6), 39-41.
4. Adamboeva, N. (2023). XUSHMUOMALALIK KATEGORIYASINI AKSIOLINGVISTIK JIHATDAN TASNIFLASH NAZARIYASI. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(7).
5. Mirzayeva, G. S. (2022). Realiyaning Nutqimizdagi Milliy Va Madaniy Koloritini Ifodalashdagi O‘rni. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 30, 349-351.
6. Shohsanam, S. K. (2023). O‘QITUVCHI MULOQOT XULQINING ICHKI FUNKSIONALLASHUVIDA OVOZNING O

- ‘RNI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(6 Part 6), 177-179.
7. Kakharova, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE TEACHER’S SPEECH IN THE CLASSROOM. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 1(6 Part 6), 173-176. Султанова, С. Р. (2023). ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПЕЙЗАЖНЫХ ОПИСАНИЙ В СТРУКТУРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(7), 987-992.
8. Султанова, С. (2023). СВОЕОБРАЗИЕ ЖЕНСКОГО ХАРАКТЕРА В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ РУССКИХ И АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПИСАТЕЛЬНИЦ В СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНОМ РАКУРСЕ. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(11).
9. Султанова, С. Р., & Давлятова, Г. Н. (2023). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВАРИАТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ РИТОРИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ. "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
10. Sultanova, S. R., & Nematov, S. X. (2023). FEATURES OF TURGENEV HEROINES IN THE APPEARANCE OF A MODERN GIRL. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(16), 113-117.
11. Sevara, S., & Timur, A. (2021). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. *Chief Editor*.
12. Sultanova, S., & Akhmadzhonov, M. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE «LITTLE MAN» IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19 CENTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 52-54.
13. Sevara, S., & Nigina, B. (2022). Degrees of Comparison of Adjective Names in Russian and Uzbek Languages. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(10), 105-108.

14. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2023). Theoretical Aspect of "Synecdoche" "As a Stylistic Figure. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 249-254.
15. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. Cultural Comparison of Uzbek and English Language Speech Styles.
16. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2021). THE BRIEF INVESTIGATION OF CONTEMPORARY SPEECH STYLES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1280-1283.
17. Vaslidin o'g'li, N. M. (2023). Main Categories of Command Speech Acts. *Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History*, 17, 85-87.
18. Дадахонова, З. (2023). ТЕСТИРОВАНИЕ КАК СПОСОБ КОНТРОЛЯ НА УРОКАХ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(10), 1970-1973.
19. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF THE SKILLS AND ABILITIES OF THE STUDENTS. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(10), 106-110.
20. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF STUDENTSKNOWLEDGE, ITS FUNCTIONS AND PRINCIPLES. *NIDERLAND" INTEGRATION, EVOLUTION, MODERNIZATION: WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION"*, 14(1).